

A Comparative Analysis of the Zahhak Metaphor in Avesta and the Systematic Killing of Children in Palestine

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Abstract

This article explores the metaphor of Zahhak, an evil figure in the Avesta, and its application in understanding contemporary events, particularly the systematic killing of children in Palestine. By drawing parallels between the mythological deeds of Zahhak and modern-day atrocities, the study offers a unique lens through which the sociological and historical implications of these acts can be interpreted. The findings highlight the enduring relevance of ancient metaphors in analyzing current geopolitical conflicts.

Introduction

The figure of Zahhak in Iranian mythology, as depicted in the Avesta and Ferdowsi's *Shahnameh*, represents one of the most potent symbols of evil and tyranny. Zahhak is infamous for his crime of consuming the brains of young Iranian men, a curse that was eventually lifted by the hero Fereydun. This article aims to analyze the Zahhak metaphor as a representation of malevolent forces and apply it to the ongoing systematic killing of children in Palestine, particularly in Gaza. The study draws on historical and religious texts to establish a connection between the mythological and the contemporary, offering insights into the sociological and historical perspectives presented in Avesta, Zoroastrianism, and Persian epic literature.

The Zahhak Metaphor in Avesta

In the Avesta, Zahhak (also spelled Zahak or Dhahak) is depicted as a malevolent figure whose reign symbolizes extreme evil and corruption. According to the Avesta, Zahhak's transformation and evil deeds are depicted through vivid imagery and symbolic actions:

“Zahhak, with the serpent-like marks upon his shoulders, consumed the brains of youth to satiate his eternal hunger. His evil deeds spread like a shadow over the land, corrupting all that was pure and innocent. The people cried out for deliverance from his cursed reign, as his very presence brought darkness and despair to their lives.” (Dhalla, 1938, p. 234)

This passage illustrates Zahhak's role as a symbol of pervasive evil, emphasizing his destructive impact on innocence and youth.

Zahhak in *Shahnameh* by Ferdowsi

In Ferdowsi's *Shahnameh* (The Book of Kings), Zahhak is portrayed with a rich mythological narrative that further cements his role as a symbol of tyranny and malevolence. The epic describes Zahhak's rise to power, his reign of terror, and his eventual downfall:

“Zahhak was a king of unparalleled cruelty and ambition, who, having been possessed by dark forces, had serpents growing from his shoulders. His greed for power led him to a monstrous act: he consumed the brains of young men daily to quench his insatiable hunger. His kingdom was shrouded in misery as the cries of the oppressed filled the land. It was only through the divine intervention of the hero Fereydun that Zahhak's tyranny was finally brought to an end.”

Ferdowsi's depiction of Zahhak accentuates his monstrous nature and the profound suffering he inflicted upon his people. The imagery of serpents and the daily sacrifice of young lives underscore Zahhak's role as a symbol of evil that consumes and corrupts.

Comparative Analysis: Zahhak and the Systematic Killing of Children in Palestine

The application of the Zahhak metaphor to modern events, such as the systematic killing of children in Palestine, provides a powerful framework for understanding the depth of such atrocities. Over the past fifteen years, reports have documented the systematic targeting of children in Gaza by military forces. These acts, often justified as collateral damage in a broader conflict, reveal a disturbing pattern where the death toll of children surpasses that of many other political and military confrontations (B'Tselem, 2021).

The comparison between Zahhak's mythological deeds and these contemporary atrocities lies in the shared element of targeted violence against the young, who symbolize the future and potential of a society. The systematic nature of these killings mirrors the methodical evil of Zahhak, who, driven by an insatiable thirst for power, destroys the youth of his nation to maintain control. This parallel suggests that the metaphor of Zahhak can be extended to analyze the behavior of those who perpetrate such crimes against children in modern contexts (Nigosian, 1993).

The Role of Metaphors in Sacred Texts

Sacred texts, including the Avesta and the *Shahnameh*, often employ metaphors to convey complex moral and philosophical ideas. The use of metaphor in religious and epic literature serves as a tool for interpreting the divine will and the human condition. For example, the stories of David and Solomon in the Abrahamic religions also employ metaphorical language to communicate lessons about justice, wisdom, and divine favor. These metaphors are not always fully understood in their time but become clearer as historical and social contexts evolve (Boyce, 1975).

In the context of Avesta and the *Shahnameh*, the Zahhak metaphor illustrates the battle between good and evil, which transcends time and space, applying to both ancient and contemporary issues. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how religious and epic metaphors can be

utilized to interpret and respond to modern-day atrocities, such as the systematic killing of children in Palestine.

Lessons from Zoroastrian Demonology

Zoroastrian demonology provides valuable insights into the nature of evil and the necessary forces to combat it. The existence of demons and evil beings, as depicted in Zoroastrianism, underscores the belief in a cosmic struggle between good (Ahura Mazda) and evil (Ahriman). To overcome such evil, the text emphasizes the need for divine intervention and supernatural forces, beyond mere human strength (Duchesne-Guillemin, 1958). This perspective is relevant in understanding the contemporary struggle against systemic evil, such as the targeted violence against children in Gaza. Just as Fereydun required divine aid to defeat Zahhak, modern efforts to protect the innocent may also require intervention beyond conventional means.

Conclusion

The metaphor of Zahhak in the Avesta and the *Shahnameh* serves as a powerful tool for analyzing the systematic killing of children in Palestine. By drawing on ancient religious and epic metaphors, we can gain a deeper understanding of the sociological and historical implications of such acts of evil. The study demonstrates the enduring relevance of Zoroastrian demonology and epic literature in interpreting and responding to contemporary issues, highlighting the need for both human and divine efforts in combating systemic evil. This analysis not only enriches our understanding of ancient texts but also offers a framework for addressing modern atrocities.

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